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Abstract

Due to unlimited consumer expectations, a changing environment, emerging new technological trends, high competition, and rivalry in the global market, companies using this challenging and uncertain era of technology need transformational leadership and work behaviors from their employees to cope successfully with uncertainties. The current research tests the effectiveness and relationships of transformational leadership and innovative work behavior with the mediating construct of intrinsic motivation. However, most recent studies in the field of creativity have mainly examined how leaders affect their team members' creativity instead of focusing on innovative work behavior. Thus, the present study concentrated on innovative work behavior through the mediating effect of intrinsic motivation for the first time in Afghanistan. The present research has applied quantitative research methodology and positivism philosophy with a deductive approach based on the available theories and concepts and used a non-probability type convenient sampling method with a maximum sample size of 210 respondents. For analysis, frequency tests, reliability tests, normality tests, and mediation analysis tests were done through SPSS. The important discoveries of the present study explored how intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior in the Afghan development sector. Future researchers could use the different mediations and mediators to enlarge and clarify the association between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior in different contexts.

Key Words: Transformational Leadership, Innovative Work Behavior, Intrinsic motivation.

Introduction

The previous study indicated that transformational leaders might encourage innovative work behaviors of the employees to generate novel ideas and bring innovation to their services (Tse et al., 2018; Rosing et al., 2011). In addition, the TL style has empowered the followers to bring innovation, tackle complicated problems, and increase innovative work behavior in the organization (Afsar, B. & Masood, M, 2018). Moreover, instead of focusing on IWB, most studies in the field of creativity research have mainly examined how leaders affect their team members' creativity (Hughes et al., 2018). A present concept in the literature is that IWB is difficult, risky, complex, and not precise, so there must be intervention variables to define the association between an individual's IWB and TL (Afsar et al., 2014; Jaiswal & Dhar, 2015; Choi et al., 201), such as employees' motivation (Qu et al., 2015) awareness concentration (Henker et al., 2015), sharing information, and a favorable organization learning climate (Masood & Afsar, 2017). For exact clarification, the current literature has mentioned that future research could take motivation as an additional factor to test the relationship between IWB and TL (Jaiswal & Dhar, 2015). In the public-sector literature, some scholars advise the importance of intrinsic motivation in transformational leadership and innovative work behavior processes. (Perry, Engbers, & Jun 2009; Jacobsen & Andersen 2017). Therefore, the proposed study compares the association between TL and IWB with the mediating role of IM.

Innovative work behavior is essential for surviving the organization in the age of globalization, a diversified economic climate, the technological era, and rising divergent expectations for high-quality services and products (Li & Hsu, 2016; Kim & Koo, 2017; Hon & Lui, 2016). Public-service organizations are trying to motivate their employees to generate and implement innovative ideas that could increase overall outcomes and quality of service (Edghiem & Mouzoughi, 2017; Li & Hsu, 2016). A good leadership style can promote innovative work behavior among the employees by implementing inspirational practices and creating a healthy organizational climate for the improvement of the employees' innovation capacity, which will raise the creative ability and competitive benefits for the company in the competitive market in the upcoming times (Patiar & Wang, 2016; Schuckert et al., 2018). Different theories have been discussed for the desirable leadership approach for enhancing IWB among individuals. Prior analyses have concentrated on the significance of the transformational leadership style. (Rawung et al., 2015; Masa'deh et al., 2015). TL is a good leadership approach for enhancing innovative work behavior in public service organizations.

Some scholars discussed novel ideas and innovation, which have a tremendous competitive advantage in public services and high-tech sectors. (Borins, 2006) Motivation is crucial for innovation in these two industries, directly related to employees' high intrinsic motivation (Chen et al., 2013). Innovation in the services and products empowers the organization to establish value and get market productivity and customer satisfaction for other competitors in the market (Kindström et al., 2013). For most organizations, boosting individual creative behaviors and adopting their creativity techniques according to the consumers' diversified expectations for the new products might be strategic objectives. In creativity studies, most studies have explored the manager's impact on employees' creativity rather than focusing on their innovative work behaviors. Making individuals engaged in producing innovative concepts is the core job of the executive managers in the organization (Hughes et al., 2018). The current literature talks about IWB, which is difficult, challenging, complex, and unknown; interfering factors could clearly define the association between an individual's transforming leadership style and an employee's creative attitude (Afsar et al., 2014; Choi et al., 2016). Motivation significantly affects innovative work behavior (Amabile, 1996; Feldman & Lam, 2010). So, intrinsic motivation is vital in enhancing employee creativity and inventiveness (Bechtoldt & Baas, 2008; De Dreu, Nijstad; Byron & Khazanchi, 2012). So, it is vital to consider intrinsic motivation as the intervening variable in the innovative work behavior study.

The transformational leader implements practices in a specific organization that can promote the interest of all employees in assisting them in achieving the collective objectives of the organization (García-Morales et al., 2012). TL is a style of management where the leader implements different applicable mechanisms to motivate, challenge, and encourage their followers to reach their full potential at work. As a result of these activities, creative work attitudes and practices might increase within the public service organization. (Bass, B.M, 1999). Finding innovative solutions for complicated problems and sustainable economic growth, transformational leadership, which might help achieve those specific aims. The previous study investigated the impact of TL on individuals' IWB and the appropriate intervention effect of job difficulty and innovation environment for the organization. The study mentioned the gap for testing the other intervening variables, which might be more useful in the IWB and TL relations. Due to the motivational states, IM has a crucial role as a core mediator between leadership and

employees' behavioral responses. For the first time, our present study tested the impact of TL on IWB with the mediating role of IM. This study is the first to consider the development sector in Afghanistan. The following are the main objectives of the current study:

- i) To investigate the impact of TL and IWB in the development sector of Afghanistan.
- ii) To measure the impact of TL on intrinsic motivation in the development sector of Afghanistan.
- iii) To investigate the impact of intrinsic motivation on innovative work behavior in the development sector of Afghanistan.
- iv) To assess the mediating role of work IM between IWB and transformational leadership.

Transformational leaders may encourage innovative work behaviors of the employees to generate novel ideas and bring innovation to their services (Rosing et al., 2011; Tse et al., 2018). A present concept in the literature is that IWB is difficult, challenging, complex, and not straightforward; therefore, intervening variables are essential to define the relationship between an individual's innovative work. The present study compares the association between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior with the mediating role of IM. This study filled the mentioned gap in the literature, which claims that most studies concentrated on creativity instead of innovative work behavior and that there is no testing on the mediating role of intrinsic motivation. Furthermore, no study addresses the relationships among the mentioned variables in Afghanistan.

2. Underpinning theory

The selection of innovative work behavior and transformational leadership variables is based on the "interactionist perspective of creativity" (IPC) framework, which explores innovation and creativity differences among the organization's employees. Based on the interactionist view, individuals' behavior is the final result of various contingency factors, the interaction of individuals, and contextual factors (Woodman et al., 1993). Consequently, individual innovative work behavior has been known as complex interactions among individual, unit, and organizational factors, which may either support or inhibit employees' initiative in work organization (Annin & Dorson, 2017; Yuan et al., 2018). (Annin & Dorson, 2017; Yuan et al., 2018). According to this IPC, the study indicated that leaders' influence on employees' innovative work behavior relies on leaders' relations with employees on multiple levels, like situational, individual, and other contextual dimensions (Koseoglu et al., 2017; Masood & Afsar, 2017). Social exchange theory also supports the relationship between the IWB and transformational leadership. The theory has the essential norms that prove the support of the transformational leader and his or her followers in different ways, like by showing constructive behaviors and attitudes and positively taking part in the organization's tasks. We could mention a few: commitment to the organization, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, work performance, and innovative work behavior (Choi, 2016).

A past study showed that transformational leadership is more valuable than other leadership styles in influencing individuals' behavior toward innovation, creativity, and performance (Banks et al., 2016; Braun et al., 2013; Deinert et al., 2015; Eberly et al., 2017; Hughes et al., 2018., 2011). Transformational leadership discusses the interaction between the leaders and followers according to the following dimensions: individual consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence

on personal, group, and organizational levels (Q. 2007, 18, 49–68). The componential theory of creativity (Amabile, 2013) explored three elements of creativity: domain-relevant skills, creativity-relevant processes, and task motivation. According to Amabile, intrinsic motivation is all those activities related to interest, enjoyment, and an individual, who feels to challenge himself or herself—more than those factors are needed for achieving favorable creative results. (Vinarski-Peretz & Carmeli, 2011). Intrinsic motivation is one of the most significant elements for promoting innovative work behaviors due to its influences on individuals' cognition, behavior, and emotions, which directly impact their functionality (Saeed, Afsar, Shahjehan, & Shah, 2019; Zhou & George, 2003). Studies on the componential theory of creativity focus on leaders providing support that might boost followers' intrinsic motivation and creativity. (Amabile, Schatzel, Moneta, & Kramer, 2004).

3. Literature review and hypothesis

Transformational Leadership and Innovative Work Behaviour

TL is multi-level interaction. In this interaction, the leader plays a significant role and looks like a role model for their employees. Leaders are trying to encourage and support IWB by inspiring employees and mentoring followers to achieve the shared objectives and vision of the company (Avolio & Bass, 1994; Bednall et al., 2018; Suifan et al., 2018). TL considers supporting and fulfilling the followers' wants and needs. This fulfillment and the creation of a supportive environment enhance their influence on the employees to be emotionally touched in the innovation process in the organization. These leaders provoke their followers' intellectual thinking by questioning their assumptions and views, which motivates them to participate in creating and implementing innovative concepts. These leaders can encourage their followers by giving them inspirational motivation (Bednall et al., 2018). Therefore, TL inspires individuals to recognize that their future belongs to the company's next generation. Further, the transformational leader can enhance organizational innovation and boost the employees' creativity process (Avolio & Bass, 1994).

Transformational leaders consider the employees' past experiences, self-interest, and organizational promotion as motivating factors to follow and achieve the shared vision. Implementing the IWB's practices is possible through intellectual motivation, emotional attachment, and encouragement in the organization by the leader. In the different stages, innovation-related objectives appear dynamic, active, and even tangible (Zuraik, Kelly, 2019). Transformational leaders may persuade employees through their imaginative initiative, practical skills, individualized coaching, supportive culture, and capacity for intellectual stimulation to engage in innovative work behavior processes (Afsar et al., 2014). Transformational leaders can establish a supportive organization through inspiration, motivation, and individualized consideration. This supportive organizational climate positively enhances individuals' encouragement to be involved in the innovation process within the organization and implement new practices for achieving the desired creative outcomes. Additionally, this environment gives support and suggestions for discovering creative and efficient solutions to complicated problems (Johannessen et al., 2001; Tse et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2014). Ma and Jiang (2018) argued that IWB is essentially boosted in corporate contexts by transformational leaders who encourage their staff to be open-minded, ambitious, risk-takers, and willing to solve new emerging problems in new ways that might be implemented in their organization for the first time. So therefore, based on the above discussion, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 1: *There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior.*

Transformational leadership and intrinsic motivation

Giving vision and inspiration to the employees are two core functions of transformational leadership (Chen CHV & Tang; YY, 2009). According to the literature on transformational leaders, the core jobs of these leaders are to guide and motivate their followers to take an active part in achieving the organization's shared goals and performances (Jensen UT, Bro LL, 2018). Transformational leaders can awaken followers' feelings about the succession of the organization and their expertise to achieve this strategic goal. Transformational leaders are responsible for boosting organizational productivity compared to the people's diversified demands and fulfilling these different expectations through developing human resources and implementing exemplary practices in the organization (Soosay & Ghasabe, 2015). The followers learning new skills for the enhancement of their productivity and their efforts for gaining essential competence directly belong to intrinsic motivation, which shows the person's willingness to do hard work to achieve the required competencies and meaningful skills (Silva WF, Redondo RP, Cárdenas. MJ, 2018). Transformational leadership styles can increase the capacity for psychological empowerment, called intrinsic motivation (Thomas, 1990). Motivation is why people do their work internally without looking for a proper reward. Intrinsic motivation is a condition "when individuals are motivated by their willingness to perform the task instead of following a contract-for-rewards approach to accomplishing the work (Chen CHV, Li HH, Tang YY,2009). The research findings, which was conducted by (Koh, Lee, & Joshi, 2019), showed that IM is highly affected by TL, as the latter instructs and effectively supports self-inspiration, which is a valuable and practicable factor of the organization's secession and creativity outcomes. TL combines four behavior factors idealized influence, the motivation that inspires, intellectual stimulation, and thoughtful regard for each person (Bass & Riggio, 2006). The four factors mentioned above have a significant impact on the individual's IM and his or her willingness to do the regular tasks differently. Transformational leaders use idealized influence to share the organization's vision by adequately communicating and providing the required inspiration and support for the team to perform the tasks creatively. The leader could quickly increase employees' intrinsic motivation (Arthur, Shamir, House & Arthur, 1993). Transformational leaders can enhance positive outcomes like high self-interest among the whole members of the group, which could boost the happiness and job satisfaction of the employee while performing related activities (Deci EL, Ryan RM, 1985). The second element of the model is intellectual stimulation; through this factor, transformational leaders can enhance the willingness of team members to become more productive and be encouraged to tackle complicated problems by themselves (Bass, BM & Riggio RE, 2006). So, therefore, based on the above discussion, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 2. *Transformational leadership positively affects intrinsic motivation.*

Intrinsic motivation and innovative work behavior

The recent literature on inspiration focused on the specific requirements for motivation, which could be helpful for the generation of novel ideas and implementation of TL at the various levels of the organization (Rego, Sousa, Marques & Cunha, 2012). Amabile et al. (1996) explained and found that intrinsic motivation could help create a process of innovative work behavior in the workplace, which could enhance the capacity of the employees to be creative in the production of new ideas and implementing those ideas in

the organizational environment for producing innovative products and bringing innovation to their services. The foundation for innovation in this emerging technological age is creative thinking. We must consider many internal and external elements to adapt the employees to think creatively outside the box. Among those, the willingness of the individuals is significant, which we can call intrinsic motivation. Furthermore, for releasing unique and novel ideas, freedom and autonomy are essential requirements of the individual, giving them the competence to bring about changes in human life and enhance the organization's productivity to produce massive, inimitable products in a brief period. The theory of self-determination (Gagne & Deci, 2005) discussed that the organization of autonomous inspiration is proved by creativity, and creativity relies on the inspiration of the individual, which the leader provides. Thus, more motivated people are intrinsically more creative (Grant & Berry, 2011). So, in a supportive environment, empowered individuals like to be more curious, generate, and implement creative ideas. Intrinsic motivation is essential for an employee to be innovative in performing complicated tasks at the workplace, bring innovation to the outcomes, and find valuable ways to solve complicated questions (Amabile, 1988; Redmond, Mumford & Teach, 1993). Therefore, IM related to innovative work behavior is accepted by research done by (Devloo et al., 2013). The componential theory of creativity (Amabile, 2013) recognized three elements: task motivation, creativity-relevant processes, and domain-relevant talents. Intrinsic motivation is engaging in enjoyable and challenging activities, and the individual is strongly willing to perform the task themselves. It is worth mentioning that this alone is insufficient to produce positive, creative results. (Carmeli Vinarsk & Peretz, 2011). Therefore, IM is a critical element of IWB due to its impact on individuals' cognition, attitude, and inspiration, which can directly enhance their creativity outcomes at the workplace (Afsar, Saeed, Shahjehan, & Shah, 2019; Zhou & George, 2003). So, therefore, based on the above discussion, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 3. Intrinsic motivation positively affects innovative work behavior

Intrinsic motivation mediates between Transformational leadership and IWB.

The IPC model has considered intrinsic motivation essential for constructing its central theme. The followers' or individuals' decision to engage in the organization's innovation efforts depends on their intrinsic motivation (Woodman, Schoenfeldt, 1990; Woodman et al., 1993). Besides that, their idealistic influence and stimulating intelligence can raise the employee's IM and motivate them to engage in the organization's creative process (Braun et al., 2013; Kark et al., 2018). The transformational leader could develop a good climate in the organization and foster intrinsic motivation in the employees, which is helpful in the innovative process of the organization. Transformational leadership tries to create a climate in the organization that can motivate employees to take on challenges by performing complicated activities and improving the enjoyment and engagement of employees' jobs (Golden, Shriner, 2017; Henker et al., 2015). This supportive climate guides the individuals to be part of the process of creativity in the organization and to look for innovative results (Ma & Jiang, 2018). Moreover, (Zhang & Bartol, 2010) discussed that transformational leaders boost individuals' innovation capabilities by giving them psychological autonomy, which enhances employees' intrinsic motivation (Devloo et al., 2014). Research indicates that individuals with high intrinsic motivation are more likely to engage in innovative work behaviors because they can efficiently perform their activities. It is assumed that IM may mediate in transformational leaders' influence on employees' innovative work behavior (Denti & Kark et al., 2018; Hemlin,

2012). Therefore, based on the theoretical discussion and recent study evidence, the current study hypothesis that:

Hypothesis 4: *Intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between innovative work behavior and transformational leadership*

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

4. Methodology

Sampling and Procedure

The present research follows quantitative research methodology to examine the relationship among the construct variables. The respondents of this study were unknown; however, the study focused on the development sector of Afghanistan and used a non-probability convenient sampling method for data collection and analysis. Moreover, the present study follows the deductive approach because it examines existing theories and literature on the same topic. This study developed the hypotheses based on the existing theories to develop the reasoning from particular to general.

Data Collection Procedures

A questionnaire is adapted based on the research items collected from (Bass, B.M; B.J. Avolio,1995; De Jong & Den Hartog, 2010; Ryan, R. M.,1982) already developed and adapted from the mentioned sources. The respondents from the development sector of Afghanistan and those who are related to some extent to this particular sector were asked to provide their responses on a structured questionnaire on a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The population of this study is employees working in the development sector of Afghanistan and those who have an involvement in the development sector either directly or indirectly in Afghanistan. As a result of the lack of transparent and accurate data to indicate how many people are involved in this particular sector, the researcher selected the Rule of Thumb method for specifying the sample size. There are 21 items in the present study; therefore, the researcher collected data from at least ten respondents for every item, so the sample size for the current study is 210 respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender				
Male	146	69.5	69.5	69.5
Female	64	30.5	30.5	100.0
Age				

Below 25	38	18.1	18.1	18.1
26-35	104	49.5	49.5	67.6
36-46	41	19.5	19.5	87.1
46 or Above	27	12.9	12.9	100.0
Education				
School Graduate	11	5.2	5.2	5.2
Bachelor	103	49.0	49.0	54.3
Master	87	41.4	41.4	95.7
Ph.D.	9	4.3	4.3	100.0
Work Experience				
Less than two years	43	20.5	20.5	20.5
3-5 Years	43	20.5	20.5	41.0
6-9 Years	64	30.5	30.5	71.4
10 Years or Above	60	28.6	28.6	100.0
Organizational Type				
Public	85	40.5	40.5	40.5
Private	125	59.5	59.5	100.0

The first table indicates the respondents' percentage and ratio based on gender. The data was collected from 210 respondents, both male, and female. The table showed that 146 are male, 69.5 percent of all participants, and 64 are female, 30.5 percent of all participants. Based on the table, the majority portion is male, 69.5% (n = 210), and the female portion is 30.5% (n = 210). Based on the age of the respondents, 18.1 percent means that from all respondents, 38 participants are below the age of 25, 49.5 percent means 104 respondents are between 26 and 35 years old, 19.5 percent means 41 respondents are between 36 and 46 years old, and 12.9 percent means 27 participants from all respondents are 46 or above. The table shows that among the 210 respondents, the majority are between 26 and 35 years old, which means the young generation of society made a significant contribution in responding to this questionnaire.

Further, according to the above table, 49.0 percent means 103 respondents are bachelor's graduates, 41.4 percent means 87 respondents are master's degree holders, 5.2 percent means 11 participants have high school qualifications, and 4.3 percent means nine respondents reported that they were pursuing a Ph.D. degree at the moment of giving responses to this questionnaire. The bachelor's degree holders made a significant contribution. The above table indicated that 20.5 percent means that 43 participants of all respondents have less than two years of experience, 20.5 percent means that 43 participants of all respondents reported that they have 3 to 5 years of experience during the survey, 30.5 percent means that 64 participants have 6 to 9 years of experience, and 28.6 percent means that 60 respondents of all respondents are having more than ten years of professional experience while responding to the questionnaire. In addition, as the table shows, 40.5 percent means 85 participants of all respondents who answered the questionnaire were working in public or governmental organizations. A significant portion of the respondents was working in private organizations, which means 125 participants working in private organizations.

Measurements

The study has taken the measuring instruments from previous research to maintain the study's reliability and validity. Transformational leadership is measured by five items, which have been taken from four subscales (idealized influence, individualized consideration, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation) (Bass, B.M; B.J. Avolio, 1995). Innovative work behavior is measured through 10 items, which have been taken from the study (Jong & Hartog, 2010). Intrinsic motivation is measured by six items,

which have been taken from Ryan (1982). The details of the questionnaire are presented in the table in appendix.1.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics, Mean, Standard Deviation, and Correlation

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3
Intrinsic motivation	4.4365	.85386			
Innovative work behavior	3.9214	.82018	.323		
Transformational leadership	3.4333	.86452	.345	.356	

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

We have given values of 1 to disagree strongly, 2 to disagree, 3 to be neutral, 4 to agree, and 5 to strongly disagree; therefore, according to the (2) table, the intrinsic motivation mean value is 4.4365, which indicates that respondents strongly agree with the existence of intrinsic motivation in the development sector of Afghanistan. The innovative work behavior means the value is 3.9214, which indicates that participants in the present study agree with innovative work behavior in their organizations. Transformational leadership's mean value is 3.4333, which shows that the respondents agree with the existence of transformational leadership in development sector organizations.

Further, the researcher used the non-parametric Spearman test for the correlation analysis because the data were non-normal. According to table (2), the correlation analysis findings indicated that the correlation result for TL is positively correlated with innovative work behavior ($r=0.356^{**}$, $p<0.01$). The correlation result for transformational leadership is positively correlated with intrinsic motivation ($r= 0.345^{**}$, $p<0.00$). Furthermore, the correlation result for intrinsic motivation is positively correlated with innovative work behavior ($r=0.323$, $p<0.02$).

Table 1:Reliability Analysis for every item

Variables	Number of items	Items Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
Innovative Work Behavior	10	0	.936
Transformational Leadership	5	0	.891
Intrinsic Motivation	6	0	.939

Interpretation: The (3) table indicates the result of Cronbach's alpha for each construct. Based on Uma Sekaran's explanation in his reputed book Research Method for Business, any greater value than 0.6 is acceptable as a reliable value, so the innovative work behavior value is significant. The transformational leadership value is greater than 0.6, so it shows its reliability, and the intrinsic motivation value is also greater than 0.6, so it is accepted as reliable.

Normality

Normality testing is the first phase of analyzing the data and showing whether the data collected for the present study is usually distributed. After we know the result of the normality test, we decide whether to use the parametric or non-parametric tests for further processing. Various tests are available to test the normality, but the present study used Mardia's multivariate normality to indicate whether the data is average or non-normal.

According to Kline (Kline, 2011), the univariate skewness and kurtosis range should be (± 1 , ± 3). The skewness value should be ± 1 , and the kurtosis value should be ± 3 . For the

multivariate, the skewness and kurtosis range is between ($\pm 3, \pm 10$). The skewness value should be ± 3 , and the kurtosis value should be ± 10 .

Table 4: Skewness and Kurtosis

Variables	Skewness	Kurtosis
IWB	-1.391	0.766
TL	-.587	-.876
IM	-1.460	1.204

N=210

Interpretation: Based on Mardia's multivariate normality test and the univariate skewness and kurtosis, for innovative work behavior, the skewness (-1.391) is more significant than minus one, and the kurtosis (0.766) is less than one, so it is non-normal and highly skewed. The data for transformational leadership, skewness (-0.587), and kurtosis (-0.876) are less than one, so it is normal and moderately skewed. The data for intrinsic motivation is skewness (-1.460) and kurtosis (1.204), which are more significant than one, so it is non-normal and highly skewed. There are three variables in the current study, so we tested the reliability through Mardia's multivariate skewness and kurtosis. As the above figure (2) shows the multivariate test result, which indicated that both skewness (4.614406) and kurtosis (16.559640), which are greater than the range between ($\pm 3, \pm 10$), indicate that the data is non-normal, we had to apply the non-parametric test. However, the researcher used the Andrew F. Hayes Andrew for regression mediation analysis and hypothesis testing.

Regression and Mediation Analysis

To investigate the relationship between the independent variable TL and dependent variable IWB with the meditating effect of IM through Andrew F. Hayes Andrew regression mediation process. The following tables indicate those relationships.

Table 4: The main effect, mediated, and regression analysis TL &IM

Outcome Variable: IM							
Model Summary							
	R	R-sq	MSE	F	Df1	Df2	p
	.4961	.2462	.5522	67.9195	1.0000	208.0000	.0000
Model							
	Coeff	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	
Constant	2.7541	.2105	13.0846	.0000	2.3391	3.1691	
TL	.4900	.0595	8.2413	.0000	.3728	.6072	

The R-square value is 0.2462, meaning there will be a 24 percent change in intrinsic motivation due to transformational leadership. It has been mentioned as being worth that; it is significant because its P value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the finding result, the overall model is also accepted. The beta coefficient indicates that one unit change in TL will bring a 0.49 increase in the medium variable intrinsic motivation. The coefficient of the regression is significant as well because the P value is less than the level of significance.

Table 5: The main effect, mediated, and regression analysis

Outcome Variable: IWB							
Model Summary							
	R	R-sq	MSE	F	Df1	Df2	p
	.6768	.4581	.3681	87.4857	2.0000	207.0000	.0000
Model							
	Coeff	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	
Constant	.9585	.2320	4.1312	.0001	.5011	1.4160	

TL	.3495	.0559	6.2511	.0000	.2393	
IM	.3974	.566	7.0200	.0000	.2858	.5090

Interpretation: The R-square value is 0.4581, which means there will be a 45 percent positive change in the IWB as the result of both the independent variable transformational leadership and the mediation variable intrinsic motivation, which affect innovative work behavior by 45 percent. It is valuable to remember that both are significant because their P values are less than 0.05. Based on the finding result, the overall model is also accepted. The beta coefficient value shows that one unit change in the TL will bring a 0.34 change in the dependent variable IWB behavior. One unit change in mediation will bring a 0.39 unit change in innovative behavior. The coefficient of the regression is significant as well because the P value is less than the level of significance. Further, the outcome indicates a partial mediation effect of intrinsic motivation between TL and IWB.

Table 6: Main effect, mediated & regression analysis of IWB, TL& IM

The total effect of X on Y							
Effect	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI		
.5442	.539	10.1001	.0000	.4380	.6504		
Direct effect of X on Y							
Effect	Se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI	C'_ps	C'_cs
.3495	.0559	6.2511	.0000	.2393	.4597	.4261	.3684
Indirect effect (s) of X on Y							
Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI				
IM	.1947	.0427	.1163	.2837			

Interpretation: based on the above table, the direct effect of TL on IWB is positive and significant, according to (Hayes, 2013). if the P value is less than 0.05 and the upper limit interval and lower limit interval are positive, the relationship between the variables is positive and significant. For the mediation, the indirect effect of TL means the independent variable on IWB means the dependent variable is 0.1947, and both the upper and lower limit interval is positive. Based on the findings, the IM mediates the relationship between TL and IWB.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The present study was conducted in the development sector of Afghanistan. The participants in the research were those related to this particular sector. For analysis, frequency tests, reliability tests, normality tests, and mediation analysis tests were done through SPSS. The important discoveries of the present study explored the fact that IM mediates the relationship between TL and IWB in the development sector organizations. Reputable studies agree with what the regression analysis found about TL and TL. TL increases motivation, morale, and innovation by using different practices. Bednall (2018) mentioned that the transformational leader's attention to supporting the employees' expectations and requirements could enhance their influence on the followers and make them emotionally touched by the innovation process in the organization. He adds that these leaders inspire followers' intellectual thinking by challenging their beliefs and assumptions, which motivates followers to participate in creating and implementing innovative concepts for the organization's long-term survival in this competitive market. These kinds of leaders can encourage their followers by giving them inspirational motivation. According to the Bass and Avolio (1994) study about the potential of transformational leaders, they can inspire individual employees to recognize their future as belonging to the long-term success of the company and take active contributions in the

generation and implementation of innovative practices within the organization under any challenging and complicated conditions. According to a study by Afsar (2014) about TL and IWB, transformational leaders' capacity for intellectual stimulation, functional understanding, tailored mentoring, an encouraging culture, and innovative ideas can influence innovative work habits. (et al., 2014; Ma & Jiang, 2018). Previous empirical studies have suggested that transformational leaders foster an environment where workers can experiment, take calculated risks, and communicate openly. The current study, through these findings, explores how transformational leadership positively and significantly impacts IWB.

The mediation and regression analysis findings indicated that TL positively and significantly affected IWB. The core responsibilities of transformational leaders are influencing the followers, giving them a particular vision of the organization's strategic objectives, and motivating them to pursue and achieve these specific objectives. Because of what they found, transformational leaders give their employees the motivation they need to do their jobs well and efficiently. (Thomas & Velthouse, 1990) mentioned that the TL could increase a person's capacity for psychological empowerment, which is the employee's intrinsic motivation to achieve specific tasks within the organization differently. Current research by (Koh et al., 2019) found that TL significantly impacts intrinsic motivation because it effectively directs and promotes self-motivation, a valuable and practicable factor in the organization's secession to fulfill the customer's diversified expectations. Bass & Riggio (2006) suggest that TL combines four behavior factors: "idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration." These all For example, the four factors mentioned above have varying effects on employees' intrinsic motivation. Transformational leaders use idealized influence on the organization's vision by communicating the organization's vision and providing the team with different tasks to increase the intrinsic motivation of individuals, and further Transformational leaders can increase significant results and high levels of self-interest across all team members, which could increase the gratification and job contentment for performing the related task (Ryan, 1985). Transformational leadership and intellectual stimulation could boost the confidence of team members to build more productive emotional inner feelings for tackling complicated problems by themselves, without considering any financial rewards; they would have inner motivation for performing the task and bringing an innovative solution to the table for solving and handling the complicated problems. The current study explores how transformational leadership positively and significantly impacts intrinsic motivation through these findings.

Amabile et al. (1996) have explored that intrinsic motivation could be helpful in the capacity process of innovative work behavior in the organization, which could enhance the capacity of the employees to be creative in producing new ideas and implementing those ideas in the organizational environment for producing innovative products and bringing innovation to their services to meet the various needs of their clients. He further said that intrinsic motivation is more valuable than extrinsic motivation as the result of the more emotional attachment of the employees to their functions and tasks. According to Grant & Berry (2011), more motivated people are intrinsically more innovative because they want to be curious and creative to find new solutions for new and complicated problems. Moreover, Devloo et al. (2013) confirmed that intrinsic motivation encourages and increases the TL of the individuals in the organization to generate novel ideas to solve complicated tasks and bring innovation to their daily operations. Intrinsic motivation,

which affects an employee's cognition, behavior, and emotions and directly affects their performance, is a core requirement for innovative work behaviors of individuals to be innovative and generate unique solutions in this technological era, where without innovation it will be tough to survive for an extended period.

The mediation regression analysis result indicated that intrinsic motivation mediates the association between transformational leadership and innovative work behavior. Furthermore, (Gong, Huang, & Farh, 2009) explored that followers of transformational leaders were more self-confident and performed their tasks with more critical and creative practices than followers who were managed in the specific group with different leadership styles. According to (Syafii et al., 2015; Saputro & Siagian, 2017) study about employee performance argued that intrinsic motivation would mediate the association between leadership style and employee performance to be involved in the creative practices of the organization. Further, Zhang and Bartol (2010b) explained that transformational leaders enhance employee creativity by fostering psychological empowerment, which increases employees' intrinsic motivation. Devloo et al. (2014) reported that individuals with high intrinsic motivation are willing to participate actively in innovative work behavior initiatives because they can efficiently perform their activities. The present study indicates a mediation process of intrinsic motivation by which the transformational leader affects employees' creativity. The present study explored, through these findings, how intrinsic motivation positively and significantly mediates TL and IWB in the development sector of Afghanistan.

Theoretical Implications

The current research findings add particular points to the current literature on creativity. Although many studies have recently conducted research regarding creativity and its results, only a few studies have concentrated on innovative approaches or creativity process involvement (Du et al., 2016; Henker et al., 2018). The findings of the present research help promote the understanding of the multi-dimensional impact of creative work behavior from a multi-level view instead of studying creative outcomes alone by defining the effect of transformational leadership on employees' creative process involvement. As indicated, the employee's creative process is strongly influenced by TL and increased by IM.

Practical Implications

Moreover, the present study suggests some practical implementation for the manager and other individuals working for several organizations in Afghanistan. The present study's findings indicate that TL significantly and positively affects employees' IWB and creative process engagement. Thus the manager could implement the various multi-dimensional skills of transformational leadership to enhance the employees' creativity for generating novel ideas and solving complicated problems within the organization. The manager should provide promotion, new skills learning, empowerment, inspiration, and learning opportunities for their employees and enhance their participation in the decision-making process, so these factors will motivate them intrinsically and increase their willingness to take active participation in the innovative process, concentrate more, and show innovative work behavior in their actions. It will also help the employees generate valuable ideas in this technological era to solve the most complicated problems in new ways and meet their clients' diversified expectations. The current study will provide managers with valuable insight into how to beat their competitors.

Limitations and Future Directions

Despite the significant findings, the present study has its limitations as well. The researcher collected the data through non-probability convenience sampling, in which the target population has not had the right to be selected equally for answering the questionnaire; therefore, it will give an obvious result if we target a specific population and use the convince sample method for every respondent to have equal rights to share their concerns and views about the TL and IWB within the particular organization. Future researchers could use the different mediators and moderators to learn more about the relationship between TL and IWB in different workplaces and make it more transparent. On the other hand, it will give managers more options and factors to use together for the best productivity and to come up with new ideas in a constantly changing world and becoming more innovative. For further details and enlargement, the moderating construct might bring valuable and vital results that have not yet been explored; in the result, a moderator is a factor that impacts the relation between the independent and dependent variables (Saunders et al., 2016). There should be intervening variables to explore the relationship between transformational leadership and an individual's innovative work behavior since it has been established by a recurrent theme in the literature that IWB is arduous, challenging, complex, and unclear (Afsar et al., 2014; Jaiswal & Dhar, 2015). Like personal inspiration (Qu et al., 2015), promotion concentration (Henker et al., 2015), and a favorable organizational learning climate (Masood & Afsar, 2017), thus the future researcher could select one of the variables mentioned earlier to clarify the relation furthermore. Their study could explore factors that can give strength or weakness to the relationship between TL and IWB. In addition, future researchers could conduct research in other sectors of Afghanistan to explore the impact of the mentioned variables in a different environment and share the outcomes of their research with other managers to boost innovation in their related organizations' products and services.

Authors Contributions

The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: study conception, data collection, model evaluation: RKJ; analysis, and design: ANN; interpretation of results and draft manuscript preparation: HBZ. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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